

Complexing behavior of 2-amino-4-benzamidothiosemicarbazide towards some 3d-metals

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Some new complexes of Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} have been synthesized with 2-amino-4-benzamidothiosemicarbazide. All the complexes have 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratio with non-ionic nature except the Fe^{III} complex, which is 1 : 1 electrolyte. All are found to be paramagnetic high spin complexes with octahedral geometry involving sp^3d^2 hybridization in which the ligand behaves as (NNS) mononegative tridentate one complexation takes place via the nitrogen atom (primary amine), amido nitrogen atom and thiol sulfur atom.

In view of the biological activities of thiosemicarbazides¹ which possess dual donor sites with sulfur and nitrogen atoms available for coordination with metals, efforts have been made to synthesize *N*-amino derivatives of thiosemicarbazide. In this communication, we report the synthesis and characterization of Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with 2-amino-4-benzamidothiosemicarbazide.

Results and discussion

Results of chemical analyses and conductometric titrations (both direct and reverse) corresponded to 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratio in all the complexes (Table 1). Furthermore, molar conductivity data ($15-35 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) in $10^{-3} M$ DMF solutions proved the non-ionic nature of all the complexes except Fe^{III} which was found to be 1 : 1 electrolyte ($80 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$).

Table 1. Analytical and magnetic data of complexes*

Compd.	Colour	Metal% :		μ_{eff} B M.
		Found	(Calcd.)	
[C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₁₀ S ₂]Mn	Yellow	10.95	(10.91)	5.86
[C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₁₀ S ₂ Cl]Fe	Brown	10.27	(10.35)	5.89
[C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₁₀ S ₂]Co	Brown	11.72	(11.61)	3.80
[C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₁₀ S ₂]Ni	Green	11.65	(11.58)	2.89
[C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₁₀ S ₂]Cu	Green	12.34	(12.41)	1.85

*All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

IR spectrum of ABTSC (KBr) showed bands at 3357 and 1519 (NH, asym. stretch and N-H def. due to primary amine)², 3242 (NHNH₂-hydrazine group)³, 1629 (NH₂ bend in amide)⁴, 1253 (C=S) and 958 cm⁻¹ (C-S)⁵. ABTSC behaved as mononegative tridentate ligand via nitrogen atom

(primary amine), amido nitrogen atom and sulfur atom of SH with the replacement of hydrogen atom from the latter.

The mode of complexation through primary amine was supported by the disappearance of 3357 cm⁻¹ band in all the metal complexes except in nickel complex (3327 cm⁻¹) and lowering shift of N-H (def.) frequency of the same group at 1480-1504 cm⁻¹. Moreover, all the complexes have failed to respond the diazo test, suggesting involvement of primary amine nitrogen on complexation. Lowering shift in the region 1608-1616 cm⁻¹ confirmed coordination through amido nitrogen atom. Also a red shift of the ν C=S band (1190-1240 cm⁻¹) and disappearance of γ C-S band were a result of coordination through sulfur atom. However, this fact of complexation via SH group can not be explained by the emergence of new band due to C=N because of combined frequency of coordinated nitrogen atoms of amide and amino group. Non-involvement of hydrazine group (3242 cm⁻¹) in complexation was ruled out by the blue shift of this frequency at 3262-3375 cm⁻¹. New absorption bands appeared in the far IR region at 418-480 (M-N)⁶ and 390-400 cm⁻¹ (M-S)⁷.

The electronic spectra of the Mn^{II} complex showed absorption bands at 14090, 16550, 19700 cm⁻¹ assigned to the transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(G)$, respectively, suggesting an octahedral geometry around the central metal ion⁸. In the spectra of the Fe^{III} complex, the bands at 14100, 20000 and 23809 cm⁻¹ correspond to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(G)$ transitions, respectively, suggesting an octahedral geometry⁹. The spectra of the Co^{II} complex exhibited bands at 9500, 18000 and 20833 cm⁻¹, assigned to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)(\gamma_1)$, ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}(F)(\gamma_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow$

${}^2T_{1g}(P)$ (γ_3), which suggested an octahedral geometry around the central metal ion¹⁰. The Ni^{II} complex exhibited three absorption bands at 10630, 17900, and 25000 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(\nu_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(\nu_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$, respectively, suggesting an octahedral geometry around the nickel ion¹¹. In the Cu^{II} complex, the band observed at 15500 cm^{-1} , assignable to ${}^3E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_g$ transition, indicate distorted octahedral structure¹².

All the complexes were found to be paramagnetic with magnetic moment values (Table 1) corresponding to the spin only value of unpaired electron. These values are in close agreement with the reported values in high spin octahedral complexes involving sp^3d^2 hybridization. On the basis of above dissertations, octahedral geometry has been assigned to these complexes.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade except methyl anthranilate (Koch-Light). 2-Amino-4-benzamidothiosemicarbazide (ABTSC) was prepared by treating successively the acid hydrazide (obtained by the hydrazinolysis of methyl anthranilate) with carbon disulfide, sodium monochloroacetate and hydrazine hydrate using liquid ammonia as solvent. The product was crystallized from hot ethanol (75%).

Fresh solution of ABTSC in double-distilled water was always used. Stock solutions of metal salts (manganese chloride, ferric chloride, cobaltous chloride, nickel chloride and copper acetate) were prepared in distilled water and their strengths verified by usual methods¹³. The solution of desired strengths were made by dilution with water.

Electrometric titration of the ligand alone and metal-ligand mixtures were performed to decide the stoichiometry of the complexes. All the complexes were isolated by mixing equimolecular solution (0.05 M) of the metal salts and ABTSC in 1 : 2 ratio and raising pH of the resulting solutions to 9 with aqueous ammonia. The complexes were filtered,

washed with water, crystallized from dimethyl sulfoxide and dried over P_2O_5 in a vacuum desiccator. The complexes were analysed and characterized by molecular weight determinations at U.S.I.C., University of Roorkee, Roorkee (Beckmann's cryoscopic method) using ethanol solvent, magnetic measurements, electronic and IR spectral studies. Instruments used : Beckmann's apparatus for molecular weight determinations; Philips conductivity bridge with dip type conductivity cell; Toshniwal CL-49 pH-meter; Gouy's magnetic balance C-Meltov Zoric H6; electronic spectra (ethanol), Shimadzu 1601 C.P. spectrophotometer; IR spectra (KBr/nujol), Perkin-Elmer 1600 FTIR spectrophotometer.

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